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**SUBJECTIVE WELL-BEING AND PSYCHOLOGICAL HEALTH OF TEACHERS:
SOME THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL ASPECTS****Olena BONDARCHUK***SHEI "University of Educational Management", NAES (Kyiv, Ukraine)*

The article deals with the problem of the correlation between subjective well-being and psychological health of teachers. It is shown that the problem of the relationship between subjective well-being and health in general is characterized by both potentially extremely important findings, and also by pivotal research issues and questions. The basic principles of the study of psychological health are determined. The main criteria and indicators of psychological health are highlighted. Groups of factors of subjective well-being of teachers that are directly related to their psychological health are identified. Distinctive features of teachers that can negatively affect their psychological health and subjective well-being are identified. The expediency of monitoring the subjective well-being of teachers as an important condition of identifying and maintaining their psychological health in the extreme conditions of nowadays is shown.

Keywords: *subjective well-being, psychological health, teachers.*

**STAREA DE BINE ȘI SĂNĂTATEA MENTALĂ LA CADRELE DIDACTICE:
ASPECTE TEORETICE ȘI PRACTICE**

Este abordată problema ce vizează relația dintre percepția stării de bine și sănătatea mentală la cadrele didactice. Sunt evidențiate rezultate foarte importante privind relația dintre percepția stării de bine și sănătatea mentală, fiind trasate câteva direcții și probleme de cercetare în acest sens. În același context, au fost identificate principiile de investigare a sănătății mentale, criteriile și indicatorii acesteia, inclusiv factorii care determină relația dintre starea de bine și sănătatea mentală la cadrele didactice. Se mai arată care sunt condițiile specifice ce pot afecta în sens negativ sănătatea mentală și starea de bine, autorul concluzionând că, în condițiile actuale, monitorizarea stării de bine reprezintă un aspect esențial în vederea menținerii sănătății mentale a cadrelor didactice.

Cuvinte-cheie: *stare subiectivă de bine, sănătate mentală, cadre didactice.*

Introduction

The psychological health of the individual acquires special importance as an essential factor in the constructive living of stressful and crisis situations, the "recovery" of society through the resistance of the individual to the adverse effects of the social environment. Accordingly, the issue of indicators of psychological health is relevant, which, in our opinion, can include subjective well-being, more specifically, how it is perceived and experienced. Subjective well-being represents one of the leading conditions and consequences of the formation, full functioning, development and self-actualization of personality. In this regard, the study of the professionals' subjective well-being and its factors in the context of sanogenic personal potential becomes relevant.

Subjective well-being is especially important for teachers, who are called to create favourable conditions for the development of the personality of future generations. At the same time, these are the main contradictions in the activities of Ukrainian educational organisations, which negatively affect the subjective well-being of teachers, in particular, between:

- declared values and realities of today (problems of "survival" in conditions of severe external competition, dehumanisation of relations, opposition of man and organisation);
- global market requirements, rapid and continuous organisational and technological changes and organisational potential; and the state of training specialists with strict specialisation and limited liability;
- society's requirements for the teacher's personality in terms of educational innovations and the real state of personal readiness of educators for professional activity, on the one hand, and insufficiently high status of the teacher in the Ukrainian society, on the other hand.

This can negatively affect both the subjective well-being and psychological health of teachers and, as a consequence, the quality of their pedagogical activities.

Theoretical bases of investigation

It should be noted that some aspects of the research problem have already been the subject of attention of researchers. Thus, a number of works (E.Diner [1], A.White [2], etc.) are devoted to the conceptualisation of subjective well-being, created methods for assessing both the general subjective well-being and its individual components (C.Keyes, M.Waterman [3], etc.), studied demographic and other external correlates of subjective well-being (P.Wang, T J. VanderWeele [4], etc.), judgemental process of subjective well-being; and their methodological implications. (D.Kahneman, E.Diener, N.Schwarz [5], etc.). Studies have been conducted on subjective and psychological well-being as a result of personal experience of successes or achievements in professional realisation, harmony in personal life, realisation of personal potential, self-knowledge (M.Argyle [6], C.Riff [7], etc.).

On the other hand, the conceptual ideas about personal and psychological health (B.Bratus [8], S.Maksimenco [9], etc.) are defined in the context of conceptual assumptions of positive psychology (M.Seligman [10], etc.), multi-dimensional model of personal and psychological health (C.Riff [11], etc.), theory of self-determination: autonomy, competence and connections with others (R.Ryan, E.Deci [12], etc.); substantive freedom as the ability of people to live the lives that they value (A.Sen [13], etc.). Psychological conditions for ensuring the psychological health of the staff of educational organisations has been studied by L.Karamushka, etc. [14].

However, the subjective well-being and psychological health of teachers, despite the relevance of the study, has not been studied enough. At the present stage of the development of the problem of subjective well-being and psychological health, there is no strict differentiation of these terms, since there is no description of the differences between them and no recommendations for the scope (E.Laktionova, M.Matyushina [15], etc.). And the problem of the relationship between subjective well-being and health in general is characterised by both potentially extremely important findings, and also by pivotal research issues and questions (E.Diener, S.D. Pressman, J.Hunter, D.Delgado-Chase [16]).

The purpose of the investigation is to substantiate the relationship between subjective well-being and psychological health of teachers.

The results of theoretical analysis of the problem and discussion

In general, we can talk about a diverse study of the phenomenon of health, in particular:

- health as a systemic quality: characterises human being in its integrity, which presupposes the integrity of the scientific vision;
- health as a subject of interdisciplinary research, which presupposes a multidimensional study and it is impossible to limit any particular aspect;
- health as a complex and global socio-cultural phenomenon: as a basic value it is recognised in almost all cultures, and as a result, we are talking about the perceptions of health in one specific society; in every society there is a certain resistance and immunity to the "unfriendly inflow" of the "social ailments", making health a priority, and a social value;
- health as a systemic quality: characterizes human being in its integrity, which presupposes the integrity of the scientific vision [17].

There are 3 levels of personality health: 1) physical (physical health); 2) mental (mental health), 3) social and spiritual (psychological health).

Psychological health is an integrative dynamic characteristic of personality, the essence of which is the gradual awareness and acceptance of the peculiarities of their mental development, their personality, their individuality, the active position of man, his interest in his mental development, personal and spiritual growth, focus not only on external norms, but also on internal guidelines, harmonization of relations with the world (L.Karamushka [18], etc.).

The basic principles of psychological health research include:

- system approach (B.Lomov [19], etc.): rejection of the interpretation of health as not a disease, the separation of systemic rather than isolated criteria of health, consideration of health as a system that has complex, level structure.
- holism (B.Ananyev [20], etc.): psychological health as an integrative characteristic of the individual, which is formed throughout his life.
- acmeological approach (A.Brushlinsky [21], etc.): psychological health as the ability and possibility of the individual to active creative self-realization in activity.

- genetic approach: (S.Maksymenko [22], etc.): study of health in development, its formation and improvement, to predict prospects of its development

The main criteria and indicators of psychological health are: 1) psychological literacy, knowledge about the person's inner world, conditions and opportunities for its development; 2) awareness of the internal (own needs, motives, emotions, thoughts, abilities, ways of action, personal purpose in the world) and external world (realistic, free from prejudices and prejudices perception of reality); 3) determination of behaviour by motives of personal and spiritual development, self-improvement, value attitude to health in general; 4) independence, autonomy and responsibility for choosing a position, life, path, actions; 5) the most creative use of the subject of their abilities, inclinations in the process of prosocial activity by vocation; 6) constructive attitude to negative feedback and life difficulties; 7) humanistic orientation and assertiveness; 8) the ability to establish harmonious interpersonal relationships.

The consequence of having a set of these indicators is the experience of subjective well-being as satisfaction with yourself and your life in general.

We have identified the following main factors of subjective well-being of the staff of educational organisations 1) at the macro level: socio-economic stability and resourcefulness; focus on sustainable development; political freedoms; 2) at the meso level: safe educational environment; social support and quality of relations with the environment; 3) at the micro level: the value of self-development; positive thinking; emotional maturity; adequate self-esteem; ability to self-control and self-regulation; professional capacity for work [23].

Obviously the third group of factors is directly related to the psychological health of personality.

However, researchers identify the following characteristics of teachers that indicate a threat to their psychological health:

- risk group for the possibility of acquiring psychosomatic and neurotic disorders due to occupational stress and distress (V.Pahalyan [24], etc.);
- high probability of burnout (I.Friedman [25], etc.);
- feeling of dissatisfaction with their activities (over 50%) due to the discrepancy between the contribution and the expected or actual reward, status, prestige of the profession in society, etc. (T.Ronginskaya [26], etc.);
- other indicators of social adaptation compared to representatives of other professions (L.Mitina [27], etc.);
- actualisation of the social aspect in the structure of identity, predominance (over 50%) of insufficiently substantiated requirements (N.Antonova [28], etc.), professional deformations of personality (A.Markova [29], etc.).

Accordingly, the experience of subjective well-being for such teachers is quite problematic. This conclusion is confirmed by the results of our study, according to which only 28.7% of educators have a high level of subjective well-being, and 21.0% – acceptable, while more than half of educators are characterised by its reduced (31.4%) and low (18.9%) levels. The investigation found a statistically significant correlation ($p < 0.01$) between the groups of teachers with different levels of subjective well-being and their gender and length of professional service: the longer the service, the lower well-being becomes. At the same time, women, especially those with less professional work experience, have a lower subjective well-being than men [30].

It seems necessary to take the following psychological and managerial measures to ensure the psychological health of teachers: 1) monitoring the levels of subjective well-being and psychological health of participants in the educational process; 2) creating a psychologically safe educational environment; 3) providing social support and high quality relationships with the environment; 4) the organisation of special socio-psychological training for all participants in the educational process, aimed to develop their positive and critical thinking; adequate self-awareness, the ability for self-control and personal self-regulation, emotional maturity as components of psychological health.

As a discussion, it is worth quoting the words of E.Diener, a well-known researcher in the field of subjective well-being: “encouraging progress has been made in our scientific understanding of the well-being influence on health, but many important and intriguing research questions remain” [31]. In particular, despite the established links between individual indicators of subjective well-being and health, a holistic picture of the interaction of these phenomena is virtually absent. Moderators of the optimal impact of subjective well-being on health and, conversely, health on subjective well-being are poorly studied. In addition, the socio-demographic and organisational-professional factors of subjective well-being and psychological health of not only teachers but also other professional groups are insufficiently studied.

Conclusions

There is a direct relationship between the subjective well-being and psychological health of teachers. Accordingly, monitoring the subjective well-being of teachers is an important component of identifying and maintaining their psychological health. Therefore, the development of methods for studying the psychological health of teachers and their subjective well-being is relevant and acquires special significance in the current extreme conditions.

Equally important is the training of professionals who can provide the conditions for the development of teachers' psychological health and carry out appropriate monitoring.

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